

A Concept for Team Development and Optimisation

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Abstract. With the advent of computerisation in the world of work, mutually dependent developments can be seen in modern industrial societies: the enormous increase in productivity goes hand in hand with the increase in task complexity. Simple and repetitive tasks are disappearing more and more from the realm of human activities as a result of automation. Recently, we have seen an acceleration and accentuation of this development logic. Interestingly, with the introduction of artificial intelligence, the importance of human expertise in the areas of creativity, networked and analytical thinking and solving complex problems is increasing. If we want to ensure the future success of our organisations under these conditions, we must not only redefine the relationship with the members of our organisation, but also shape it in a future-oriented, success-oriented and, above all, employee-oriented way. To this end, we are presenting a concept for team development and optimisation.

Keywords: Leadership, Team development, Team optimisation, Team, Employees, Manager, Team Spirit, Team Identity, Strategies, Roles.

1 Introduction

The team development and team optimisation system we present here is the result of many years of scientific and empirical work. The aim of our endeavours was to develop a process that can be carried out autonomously by each manager, i.e. without the support of consultants or workshop leaders, and as cost-effectively as possible with their own team, as this strengthens the mutual bond on the one hand and increases the manager's leadership skills on the other.

The structured process used can be adapted to the situational and personal needs of the teams to be developed. We suggest that the line manager explains to his or her team the intention:

- a) to go through a team development process together,
- b) that this process is integrated into the normal course of operations (i.e. no additional time is required),
- c) and that this process should not only benefit the team, but also all those involved.

This process transparency is essential because it forms the basis of the relationship (to be achieved) between the manager and the team.

In addition to the individual development steps described below, it is important that the line manager has a continuous dialogue with his team and the individual team members in which the vision of the development, the desired goal and the resulting benefits

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for all are discussed. We are guided here by John Kotter's change management concept [1].

Our concept takes account of our conviction that a focus on measures aimed solely at optimising performance falls far short of the mark and cannot produce successful results in the long term. For this reason, the activities we develop always pursue objectives that are both performance-related and focused on social group cohesion as well as individual benefits in equal measure, as this is the only way an optimisation process can function successfully in the long term.

The process consists of modular components that build on each other and can be completed within a time frame of six to 18 months, depending on the functionality or dysfunctionality of the team to be developed. When designing our system, we placed particular emphasis on a hierarchically open application framework, which means that we can speak of a generic concept.

Empirical findings show that our concept produces the best results for teams of between 7 and 12 people.

2 Reasons

Various factors, such as the acceleration of technological progress due to the digitalisation of working and living environments, and in particular the drastic changes brought about by artificial intelligence, the demographic shift in industrialised countries and the resulting shortage of skilled workers, have had an intensifying effect on the development we have observed in recent decades, in which the level of demands and complexity of the tasks that employees have to cope with have increased more and more. As a result, we have to lead in a more participatory way, extend our employees' room for manoeuvre and discretion and hand over more responsibility.

This is reason enough for managers to place work on the team's performance, ability to cooperate and motivation at the centre of their activities and to associate their self-image as successful leaders with these efforts.

3 Team Status Analysis in Advance

Before team development measures can be tackled, it is essential to analyse the current state of the team. We suggest focussing on the aspects that are important for both team cohesion and team performance:

Values - Motivation, Goals, Drivers - Commitment

An emerging finding of strongly differing views on these topics within a team makes it obvious that successful co-operation is very difficult or even impossible. We have developed the «Team Commitment Tool» in order to quickly gain clarity about the team constitution and the specific discrepancies or dysfunctionalities.

One of the criteria for the analysis tool, as for all the other instruments used as part of our team building concept, was that it should be as easy to use as possible, so that

neither expensive consultants nor workshop leaders are needed, but that every manager can use the tool in their own team after just a few minutes and does not need any help with the evaluation.

It begins with each team member taking a position on the following three questions on a sheet of paper:

1. What is important to me in my job? (The issue here are the VALUES that a person has)
2. What motivates me? What goals do I have? (The issue here are the OBJECTIVES, the MOTIVATION and the KEY DRIVERS)
3. What am I committed to? What do I stand up for? (The issue here is the COMMITMENT)

After all team members have answered their questions, the leader collects the sheets and asks the team to gather around a flipchart sheet.

Fig. 1. Inside Team Commitment Tool

There are two concentric circles on this flipchart sheet, the inner one refers to the team's internal perspective, the outer one to the team's behaviour towards various external stakeholders, such as other teams, the company, customers and suppliers. Three equally sized circle segments represent the sphere of values, goals and motivation and the last segment represents commitment.

Now it's back to the same task. The team discusses together what is important to everyone when working together as a team, i.e. the values, what motivates all team members, what common goals the team has as a team and what everyone in the team feels committed to. If there is consensus in the team about the terms that express the common attitude, then these are written into the respective segment. The course of the discussion and how difficult it is for a team to agree on certain terms is in itself an indicator of the common basis of cooperation. For this reason, it is not only important that the supervisor leads the exercise, but also that he or she observes it very attentively, but does not participate in it.

Fig. 2. Outside Team Commitment Tool

In the same way, a consensus is also sought together with regard to the outside world of the team. Here too, the team members agree on what they can agree on when it comes to attitudes towards other teams, the company, customers, and suppliers. Once this exercise has been completed, which should not take more than an hour in total, the leader takes all the individual pieces of paper and the flipchart sheet and records the most important observations as a reminder of the process of this team exercise. The evaluation of the own notes and the recorded statements of the team allow a basic assessment of what needs to be worked on with the team in the coming months. This analysis should be repeated after a few months - the timing is determined by the progress made in the team optimisation process - in order to make the change perceptible.

4 Overview of the system phases

Our concept for team building and optimisation consists of four components that build on each other:

1. Standards and Values
2. Objectives and Strategies
3. Team Spirit
4. Roles and Responsibilities

These are explained in more detail in the following chapters.

Fig. 3. System Phases Pyramid

5 Implementation

5.1 Values and Standards

Once the analysis of the current state of the team has been completed, the process of team optimisation can begin.

Values and standards form the foundation [2]. Every team must be clear about its shared values, its shared convictions, its attitude beliefs, its attitude and therefore its identity. The professional world can learn a lot from sport teams [3] and music orchestras, especially in the area of identity creation, where a great deal of attention is paid to this aspect as one of the prerequisites for success.

General additional remark: Creating a team identity is one of the foundations for team development. It is important to understand that this is not about sectarian conformity or questioning the personal characteristics of team members, but that the whole is more than its parts; each team member wins individually and as a group when team cohesion and team self-image are well developed [4].

Because team identity is a social construct that we can shape at will, the question here is not only: «Who are we?» but also «Who do we want to be?»

The manager should answer the following questions for the current situation (ACTUAL state) of his or her team, after which he or she defines the team TARGET state that he or she is striving for:

- What characterises us? (= Our strengths)
- What makes us special? (= Our uniqueness)
- What is our identity? (= Who are we?)

This preparatory work is important in order to have an idea of where the team identity development should be heading for the guided exercise with the team. If there are

serious differences between the team's answers to these questions and the manager's ideas, detailed individual discussions should take place to find out why the ideas differ so much.

By developing the team identity together with the line manager, the members create a "we" philosophy.

In a second step, the team addresses the following questions:

- What is important to us?
- What do we value?

In this way, the team clarifies what everyone must adhere to, what the team stands for and what the rules are that apply to everyone. In other words: the values, the convictions and the attitude. This is where alignment is created, the common ground that binds a team together. Together with the team, the leader lays down these rules, creating a team constitution that everyone signs. It is also important that the team and the manager determine what the sanctions are if a team member does not adhere to these rules and who should monitor this (this function should be assigned to two team members).

5.2 Objectives and Strategies

Once the team has established a common foundation of standards and the development of a team identity has been initiated (Identity definition in particular is an on-going, never-ending process, because changing team constellations and the rejuvenation of a team also give rise to new ideas and requirements), the common team goals can be defined. Normally the team has a given set of performance targets, but the line manager should not only communicate these at the start of the performance review period, but also discuss them together. The open discussion of predetermined goals in particular also welds a team together. In connection with the discussion of the specified performance targets, a workshop lasting approx. 45 minutes can be held with the team, in which Stephen Covey's «Circle of Influence» [5] is used to determine what the team can and cannot influence. This demarcation helps to allocate resources correctly, increase efficiency and effectiveness and to avoid friction over matters over which the team has no influence. The distinction between «What can we influence?» and «What can we not influence?» is supplemented by the team together with the line manager by defining how they want to deal with this, on the one hand «We are working on this» and on the other hand «We are developing a positive attitude». This also happens, for example, as part of a team meeting as a process of self-understanding.

For the development and optimisation of a team, it is essential that not only performance targets are determined or predefined targets are discussed, but also that social targets are defined for the team and its members. Social goals are at least as important as performance goals because they determine whether a team improves in the long term. Discussing and recording how you want to organise social interaction, that both the *modus operandi* and the *modus vivendi* are the subject of discussion, has a beneficial effect on team cohesion.

A social team goal that is defined at the beginning of the performance period can be, for example, the agreement on how to increase team cohesion, the joint development of a culture of error or competence leadership in a specific area of expertise within the

company. However, determining the individual benefits for each team member is also an important topic. This can consist of individual career development, an increase in expertise, an expansion of the scope of action and responsibility or general empowerment. Indicators of the success of these endeavours are typically the falling fluctuation rate or the reduction in sickness-related absences.

Once the team has clarified its goals, the next step is to determine the strategy for achieving them. By jointly clarifying the questions "What is our path to the goal?" and "What are we prepared to do to achieve it?", the team defines the framework conditions for its service provision that are accepted by everyone (e.g. one weekend shift per month for everyone or similar).

This is an open discussion, moderated by the line manager, in which the team makes a voluntary commitment that applies to all members. Precisely because this character of self-commitment must not come about through coercion or manipulation, but must be based on the free and freely expressed will of the team members, it is essential that these discussions take place in an open and transparent manner. Here again, the team consciously works its way to a higher level of identification with its own work and at the same time defines the price they are willing to pay for it.

5.3 Team Spirits

Strengthening cohesion promotes the positive development of a team immensely. To strengthen team cohesion, we suggest a simple workshop exercise that can be carried out in a normal team meeting of 45 minutes. The supervisor needs two flipchart sheets for this. One sheet says «What do I want more of in our team» and the other flipchart sheet says: «What do I want less of in our team». Each team member now writes on the flipchart sheets what he or she would like to experience more or less of in the joint work.

Fig. 4. Workshop exercise "Team Cohesion"

This is a way of expressing individual discomfort or specific concerns and sending a message to the other team members. In this way, the group finds out quickly and easily where the shoe pinches and this can be discussed together and solutions can also be agreed quickly and easily. This exercise of feeling the pulse should be repeated every six months so that a team can rely on this opportunity to make a statement on the one hand, and on the other hand so that unsaid things do not pile up, but can be dealt with quickly before everyone else and with everyone else.

Team cohesion must be achieved by the whole team, even if it is usually the case that the positive alpha persons take the lead in the matter and, for example, organise events and pull the others along.

The questions that the team should clarify here are:

- How do we give each other positive energy?
- What rituals do we use to strengthen cohesion?

In this area of team cohesion, the manager should consciously take a step back and leave it to others to ensure the right mix of activities and occasions. It doesn't matter whether the manager likes the planned activities or not, the main thing is that the team feels comfortable with them. The same applies to team rituals, be it small gifts for birthdays or celebrating achieved performance targets or project milestones.

It goes without saying that not all team members have the same expectations of group social life, not everyone wants to spend their free time with their work colleagues. This is completely legitimate and must be accepted. However, we would like to point out that even the more introverted team members feel more at home in a cheerful and well-functioning team than in an indifferent and socially cold team.

5.4 Roles and Responsibilities

In order to clarify roles and responsibilities in a team the formal instruments of the job description, the clarification of tasks, competences and responsibilities as well as function diagrams and the like are important. However, as a manager (and as a team member) you should remain aware of two aspects:

1. these are usually static (once defined) provisions, such as the job description, which are only adjusted periodically in rare cases.
2. the formal definition is often not binding or clarifying enough on a day-to-day basis to have a positive influence on commitment and engagement.

In joint discussions - e.g. in an assessment of the current situation or in a goal-setting meeting - the manager discusses the following points with their employee:

- What do I have to do? (mandatory)
- What am I allowed to do? (degree of individuality)
- What should I do? (personal expectation)
- What can I do? (self-assessment)

This joint definition of the role and responsibilities of each employee in the team not only defines the content, but also provides both sides with information about mutual expectations [6], the ideas they have about each other, the room for manoeuvre that the employee has (and is granted) and what competences and potential the employee believes he or she has.

It is important that this information is accessible to all team members, because everyone should see themselves as part of the whole, but they should also know from each other what roles the other members have in the collaboration.

6 Conclusion

Every team development process is a never-ending process to improve the individual and the group. The diverse constellation of a team is changed by every departure and every new addition, and the leader must observe these changes and analyse their effects on the structure. Although changes in composition have an impact on every team, teams stabilised through development measures are more resilient to disruptions or challenges.

This newfound resilience and robustness, as well as the increased trust, stronger identification and strengthened motivation, is an added value that comes from working on and with the team.

An optimisation process benefits everyone (the team, the individual members, the leader), but also requires more attention, commitment and work.

This price is easily outweighed by the disappointments, friction and annoyance that everyone has in a dysfunctional team.

Our system aims to optimise performance and team atmosphere for the benefit of all. We are convinced that the simple handling of the process steps offers an opportunity for as many managers worldwide as possible to dedicate their commitment to this goal.

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